

Free energy relationships for the reaction series – Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation of aromatic amines

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Manuscript received online 10 May 2014, accepted 10 May 2014

Abstract : The studies are aimed at testing the validity of various free energy relationships for the reaction series, Mn^{II} catalysed periodate oxidation of substituted anilines in acetone-water medium. The progress of catalysed oxidation of twenty anilines was followed spectrophotometrically by recording the absorbance of the reaction mixture at pre-determined absorption maxima of the reaction intermediate at different time. Arrhenius equation is followed by all reactions of the series. Hammett, Exner, Taft, Van Bekkum and Sekigawa plots were found to be concave-upward while Brown and Okamoto plot is linear with good correlation. The value of reaction constant, ρ , from Brown and Okamoto plot, is -1.46 which is suggestive of retardation of reaction by the electron withdrawing groups and acceleration by the electron donating groups as well as an electrophilic attack on the anilino nitrogen by the periodate ion during oxidation process. The negative value of ρ also indicates that the electron donating substituents stabilize by resonance, a transition state having a high positive charge on the reaction center, i.e. N of the anilino group and this facilitates the bond breaking process in the transition state. Further, the ionization of anilines is not a deciding step in the reaction mechanism. The observed free energy relationships are also suggestive of same interaction mechanism being followed in the reactions belonging to this reaction series.

Keywords : Free energy relationships, Mn^{II} catalysed, periodate oxidation, aromatic amines.

Introduction

In continuation to our studies on Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation of some of the anilines¹⁻⁸, we are reporting for the first time, the studies made on twenty reactions of this reaction series with an aim to test the validity of different free energy relationships. The studies are important for developing a general understanding regarding the mechanism of the reactions involved in this reaction series, particularly related to the involvement of resonance interactions, stabilization of charge on the reaction center, significant or non-significant ionization steps etc.

Results and discussion

Rate law :

All of the reactions of this series were found to be first order in each of substrate, oxidant and the catalyst. The kinetics was studied under pseudo order conditions by keeping generally the periodate concentration in ex-

cess. Guggenheim's method was used for evaluation of pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} . Under these conditions, the kinetics was defined by the rate law (1).

$$\begin{aligned} d[C]/dt &= k_{\text{cat}} [\text{Anil}]_0 [\text{IO}_4^-]_0 [\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] \\ &= k_{\text{obs}} [\text{DMA}]_0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where, $[\text{Anil}]_0$ = initial concentration of the substrate amine, $[\text{IO}_4^-]_0$ = initial concentration of periodate (taken in excess), $k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{cat}} [\text{IO}_4^-]_0 [\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$, and k_{cat} = overall rate constant for Mn^{II} catalysed pathway. In the absence of Mn^{II}, no significant reaction occurred. The values of k_{cat} obtained at different $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$, $[\text{IO}_4^-]_0$ and $[\text{Anil}]_0$ are seen to be in good agreement and consistent with the rate law (1). This trend has been found in all reactions studied. Further, rate-pH profile shows a maximum in case of every reaction studied.

Thermodynamic parameters :

From the overall rate constants determined at four different temperatures, the values of thermodynamic pa-

rameters were determined and the mean values are given in Table 1. The value of free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) were temperature dependent. A high negative value of entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) is suggestive of solvent interactions and of the probability that the transition state may be solvated. Small value of activation energy (ΔE) is characteristic of catalysed reaction. Statistical analysis confirmed that the standard errors of enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) and ΔS^\ddagger correlate by the relation, $T_{av} = \sigma(\Delta H^\ddagger)/\sigma(\Delta S^\ddagger)$ and lead to the centre (T_{av}) of temperature range used as reported elsewhere²⁹.

the best known and most useful is the Hammett equation²⁰. It correlates reactions rates and equilibrium constants for side chain reactions of *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzene derivatives. The equation applies to a series of aromatic compounds having the same reaction center. In accordance with Hammett relationship, the rate or equilibrium constant associated with the reaction of any one of the compounds in any particular class of compounds (say, substituted anilines) may be determined from the value for the parent compound provided two parameters – reactions constant ρ and substituent constant σ ,

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters for different reactions of the series
[At pH = 4.5, $[Mn^{II}] = 1.456 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, acetone = 10.0%]

Sl. no.	Substituent	Temp. coefficient	ΔE (kJ mol ⁻¹)	A (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	$-\Delta H^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
1.	H	1.2500	18.1283	3.5956×10^9	162.3312	15.5054	66.7209
2.	<i>p</i> -Br	1.3357	23.9498	3.3689×10^{10}	143.8417	21.3269	66.7091
3.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	1.5415	35.8837	4.8059×10^{13}	101.0753	33.2608	65.1501
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	1.6690	42.0532	4.9754×10^{14}	81.5421	39.4303	65.1568
5.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	1.2430	17.5540	4.0028×10^9	163.5594	14.9310	66.5340
6.	2,3-DMA	1.2455	17.5665	1.2438×10^9	165.6522	14.9435	67.2068
7.	<i>p</i> -Cl	1.1605	12.2939	1.9258×10^8	182.1058	9.6709	67.1253
8.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	1.5835	38.0672	3.3029×10^{13}	96.3473	35.4443	65.8418
9.	4,2-CMA	1.4800	33.1512	1.7718×10^{12}	113.8430	30.5282	66.4457
10.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	1.3525	24.5203	4.7443×10^{10}	141.8061	21.8973	66.6372
11.	<i>m</i> -Cl	1.5680	35.8047	3.5589×10^{12}	106.0012	33.1817	66.6251
12.	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅	1.1928	14.5841	1.8626×10^9	172.3081	11.9611	66.3243
13.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	1.8249	48.2172	9.0743×10^{15}	61.4655	45.6359	64.6591
14.	<i>o</i> -Cl	1.6169	39.2941	7.6170×10^{12}	95.9727	36.6711	66.9505
15.	5,2-CMA	1.5813	38.2099	9.9645×10^{11}	102.3547	35.5870	67.8799
16.	2,5-DMA	1.5484	37.7065	7.8000×10^{12}	99.8634	35.0835	66.5904
17.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	1.2715	19.5121	4.4213×10^8	162.7110	16.8891	68.2244
18.	<i>N,N</i> -DMA	1.6978	43.9500	2.0538×10^{13}	82.6342	41.3271	67.3982
19.	<i>N</i> -CH ₃	1.3053	22.0375	5.2705×10^9	151.9506	19.4145	67.3549
20.	<i>N</i> -C ₂ H ₅	1.8031	49.3571	2.0460×10^{13}	69.2441	46.7341	68.5807

Effect of substituents and free energy relationships :

Much work has been done on the influence of substituents on reaction rates and linear free energy relationships (LFERs) have been proposed for many types of reaction series. The effect of *meta*- and *para*-substituents on rate and equilibria of side chain reactions of benzene have been correlated, as have rates of nucleophilic substitution reaction and solvent effects in solvolytic reactions. Of the many quantitative relationships suggested,

are known. The Hammett equation for mono substituted benzene derivatives is,

$$\log [K/K_0] \text{ or } \log (k/k_0) = \rho \cdot \sigma \quad (2)$$

Because of the availability of data, the standard reaction chosen by Hammett was dissociation equilibrium of benzoic acid in water at 25 °C, for which ρ was taken as one. In the above equation K and k represent the equilibrium constant and rate constant respectively for the reaction of benzene derivatives containing a substituent with

a constant σ while K_0 and k_0 are the equilibrium constant and the rate constant for the parent compound respectively. For di- and tri-substituted benzene derivatives, rates and equilibrium constants are also well correlated by the Hammett equation,

$$\log [K/K_0] \text{ or } \log (k/k_0) = \rho \times \Sigma\sigma \quad (3)$$

that is, the electronic influence of each substituent is separately exerted. This is not true, however, if one substituent interferes sterically with the mesomeric effect of another *ortho* to itself.

Since electron-withdrawing groups increase the strength of benzoic acids, these substituents have been assigned positive σ values, whereas electron-releasing groups have negative σ values. The value of σ for a particular group is now considered as a measure of ability of the particular group to supply or withdraw electrons. When the logarithms of rate constant (or equilibrium constant) for a reaction series are plotted against σ , a straight line of slope ρ is obtained if the electronic interactions involved resemble with those in the ionisation of benzoic acids. The ρ value measures the susceptibility of the reactions to the influence of substituents. A positive ρ indicates that the reaction is facilitated by low electron density at the reaction site, and a negative ρ implies a reaction favoured by high electron density because this susceptibility is affected by transmission of electrical effects to the reaction site, the susceptibility of the reaction to changes of electron density at the reaction site and the effect of reaction condition.

The interaction mechanism of a substituent in influencing the rate of a reaction is, therefore, believed to be of electronic origin. The mechanisms of electronic effects are not yet completely understood but there appear to be three modes of interaction : field effects, inductive effects and resonance effects.

Electronic effects that are transmitted through space are called field effects. It is not yet possible to estimate quantitatively the effects of a substituent because of the inherent approximations involved. However, we can see the field or some similar effects operating by the knowledge of a substituent constant. Inductive effects are electronic effects that are transmitted through bonds. They arise by virtue of the different electron withdrawing powers of two different atoms when bonded. The effect falls

off rapidly with chain length. Here again a qualitative estimate of the inductive effect can be made by an application of the Hammett relationship provided an allowance is made for the field effect, but separation of field and inductive effect has not been experimentally practical although it is an area of active interest.

The resonance effect is said to operate because, due to resonance, a particular substituent on the benzene ring may enhance or decrease the electron density at the *ortho*- or *para*-position. On this reasoning, it is assumed that σ_m values probably represent only inductive and field effects whereas σ_p values also include resonance effects. Thus σ_m/σ_p is taken as the measure of resonance effect.

When the reaction center adjacent to the aromatic ring involves an atom with unshared electron pairs, e.g. anilines and phenols, the Hammett equation breaks down for some substituents. In these cases, groups that can stabilize negative charge by strong electron-withdrawing resonance effects require the use of enhanced σ values, denoted as σ^- . This need is caused by an additional or enhanced resonance effect of a type impossible with the benzoates.

To study the effect of substituents in deciding the general mechanism for the reaction series under consideration, kinetic runs for twenty substituted anilines were conducted, and the rate constants as well as different thermodynamic parameters were evaluated. The results are given in Tables 1 and 2. Arrhenius equation was found to follow in case of every reaction studied by us. The kinetic data thus obtained was utilized to test the validity of Hammett relationship and its modifications.

An examination of the thermodynamic parameters for different anilines would reveal that all of these reactions are characterized by a large negative value of entropy of activation ranging from -61.47 to $-182.11 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Further, the energy of activation is low in each case. High negative ΔS^\ddagger values are usually observed for reactions in less polar solvents. The decrease in rate with decrease in dielectric constant, and the high negative ΔS^\ddagger values indicate that solvation effects are predominant in these reactions. Since the reactions under study are expected to be ion-dipole type, it is also expected that the entropy of the activated complex for all the substituted anilines should be nearly the same. However, because of the difference in the polarity of different substituted anilines

Table 2. Data for free energy relationships at 40.0 ± 0.1 °C
 [σ from Hammett²⁰, σ^0 from Taft²⁵, σ^+ from Brown and Okamoto^{23,24}, σ^n from Van Bekkum²⁶, σ_p^0 from Sekigawa²⁷ and σ^u from Exner^{22,28}]

Sl. no.	Substituent	$10^{-6} k_{\text{cat}}$ ($\text{dm}^6 \text{mol}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)	k'/k'_H	$1 + \log [k'/k'_H]$	σ	σ^0	σ^+	σ^n	σ_p^0	σ^u
1.	H	3.37	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2.	<i>p</i> -Cl	1.71	0.51	0.71	0.23	0.27	0.114	0.238	0.243	0.34
3.	<i>p</i> -Br	3.43	1.02	1.01	0.232	0.26	0.150	0.265	0.244	0.26
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	15.1	0.45	0.65	-0.17	-0.15	-0.311	-0.129	-0.100	-0.14
5.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	4.69	1.39	1.14	-0.07	-0.07	-	-0.069	-	-0.06
6.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	47.5	14.10	2.15	-0.27	-0.12	-0.778	-0.111	-0.285	-0.12
7.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	3.82	1.13	1.05	0.11	-	-	-	-	0.10
8.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	49.4	14.66	2.17	-0.25	-	-	-	-	-
9.	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅	6.85	2.03	1.31	-0.15	-	-	-	-	-

the extent of solvation should be different and hence, the experimental value of ΔS^\ddagger differs from aniline to aniline.

For verifying the validity of Hammett relationship or its various modifications, the Taft equation, Brown and Okamoto equation, Van Bekkum equation or Sekigawa's modification, the value of the corresponding substituent constants needed, namely σ , σ^0 , σ^+ , σ^n , σ^u and σ_p^0 , were taken from the literature and these values along with the value of k_{cat} , k'/k'_H and $1 + \log [k'/k'_H]$ are tabulated together in Table 2 and the corresponding plots are given in Figs. 1–6.

Fig. 1. Hammett plot.

A non-linear, concave upward Hammett plot in Fig. 1 indicates that the electron donating substituents stabilize by resonance, a transition state having a high positive charge on the reaction center²¹, which, in this case obviously, is the N of the anilino group. This facilitates the

Fig. 2. Taft plot.

Fig. 3. Brown and Okamoto plot.

Fig. 4. Van Bekkum plot.

Fig. 5. Sekigawa plot.

Fig. 6. Exner plot.

bond breaking process in the transition state. On the other hand, an electron withdrawing substituent increases the capacity of the anilino nitrogen for a more negative charge in the transition state relative to positive charge on the same nitrogen in the ground state. This facilitates the bond making process in the transition state.

If the type of curvature observed in Fig. 1 is due to resonance in the transition state, the lower rates should be obtained with the *meta*-substituents since it is these substituents that cannot interact through resonance with the reaction site in the transition state. Separate experiments were conducted and it was observed that the oxidation of many *meta*-substituted derivatives of aniline is quite slow. Thus, from this plot and from the observation that *m*-substituted anilines react much slower, it can be concluded that the transition state is formed in this reaction series with a high positive charge on the anilino nitrogen. To verify this, the Exner's plot^{22,28} between $\log k/k_H$ and σ^u was tried, which was again concave upwards (Fig. 6).

Brown and Okamoto plot (Fig. 3) shows that there exists a linear relation between $\log [k/k_H]$ and σ^+ . It suggests that the transition state formed should be with a considerable positive charge. The Taft plot (Fig. 2) and Van Bekkum plot (Fig. 4) are both non-linear curves suggesting thereby the involvement of resonance interaction in the oxidation of anilines under consideration. The Sekigawa plot between $\log (k/k_H)$ and σ_p^0 (Fig. 5) is non-linear indicating thereby that the ionisation of anilines is not a deciding step in the reaction mechanism.

Value of correlation coefficient (r) and coefficient of determination (r^2) for linear fit Hammett, Exner, Taft, Van Bekkum and Sekigawa plots are given in Table 3. It shows better correlation for Brown and Okamoto plot in comparison to other relationships. Least square method

Table 3. Correlation constants (r) and coefficient of determination (r^2) for various LFER plots

	σ	σ^0	σ^+	σ^η	σ_p^0	σ^u
r	-0.8796	-0.7577	-0.9675	-0.7397	-0.9234	-0.7704
r^2	0.7737	0.5741	0.9361	0.5472	0.8527	0.5936

was applied for evaluating the value of reaction constant ρ from Brown and Okamoto plot, which came out to be -1.46. The negative value of ρ suggests that the electron

withdrawing groups in the nucleus retard the reaction, while the electron donating groups accelerate it and an electrophilic attack by the periodate ion on the anilino nitrogen occurs for this oxidation process. A negative value of ρ for the Brown and Okamoto plot indicates the stabilization of positive charge on transition state^{23,24}. The value of ' r ' for Brown and Okamoto plot suggests that 96.75% variation in the value of $\log(k/k_H)$ is due to the effect of substituents while 3.25% variation can be attributed to other causes. The significance test was also applied to the Brown and Okamoto plot. The calculated value of ' t ' is 7.7782, which is much higher than the critical value at 0.01 significance level, suggesting thereby, that there are less than 1% chances of error in drawing the conclusions.

Experimental

Chemicals and materials :

All chemicals used were of Aldrich/E. Merck analytical reagent/guaranteed reagent grade and used after re-distillation/recrystallization. Triply distilled water was used for preparation of the solutions. Thiel, Schultz and Koch buffer³¹, consisting of different volumes of 0.05 M oxalic acid, 0.02 M boric acid, 0.05 M succinic acid, 0.05 M sodium sulphate and 0.05 M borax, was used for maintaining the pH.

Kinetic procedure :

For studying the kinetics, the reactions were studied in a spectrophotometric cell and initiated by adding temperature equilibrated NaIO₄ solution of known concentration to the reaction mixture containing the aniline, Mn^{II} and buffer and maintained at the desired temperature (± 0.1 °C). Desired temperature was maintained with the help of a high precision thermostatic control. The progress of the reaction was followed by recording the absorbance on Shimadzu double beam spectrophotometer (UV Pharmaspec-2450), at the absorption maxima of the reaction mixture (λ_{\max}). λ_{\max} was not found to change with time under experimental conditions. Table 4 gives the absorption maxima of the reaction mixtures in case of different reactions studied by us. The reactions of the series were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by taking oxidant in excess.

Preliminary observations :

On mixing the reactants, the solution becomes coloured which later changes in to another colour. On keeping for long time, it finally gives the product. These observations indicate the formation of more than one intermediate prior to the formation of final reaction product. The absorption maxima of the reaction mixtures are in visible region, while the UV-Vis spectra of IO₄⁻, substrate and Mn^{II} indicated these to show no absorption in visible region. Hence, for following the kinetics the absorbance changes were recorded at absorption of reaction mixture at which only the relatively stable reaction intermediate absorbed.

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

For different reactions of this series, the faster colour changes in the reaction mixtures relative to the separation of product on standing for long time indicates the formation of the colored intermediate on a time scale of minutes and that of the final product on a time scale of hours. The overall reaction appears to involve several steps and possibly several transient intermediates. Stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing a known excess of NaIO₄ to react with substrate. After completion of the reaction, the precipitated product was filtered out and in the filtrate unconsumed NaIO₄ was determined iodimetrically. The curve obtained in first order plot followed the pseudo-first order behaviour upto a point after which the inflexion was obtained. Inflexion was taken as the point corresponding to the completion of first stage of reaction for which the kinetic studies were made. The results indicated the stoichiometry to be 1 mole of anilines 2 moles periodate for the initial part of the reaction. As an example the reaction in case of oxidation of an anisidine can be written as follows :

Reaction mixtures containing oxidant in excess were left overnight for completion of the reaction and filtered. The filtrate was extracted with petroleum ether (40–60 °C). The extract was evaporated at room temperature and subjected to separation using TLC. The remaining part of the filtrate might be containing other products of this reaction that could not be separated and identified. The

separated compounds were recrystallized in petroleum ether and characterized on the basis of test for quinone, melting point, UV-Vis, IR and ¹H NMR spectral studies¹⁻¹⁹. The details of the characterization studies are not being discussed in this paper. The main reaction products for the reactions of the series are given in Table 4.

it is necessary to ascertain by independent method that the reaction conforms to the first order behaviour.

Evaluation of overall rate constant :

The reactions of the series were found to be first order in substrate, Mn^{II} and periodate each. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were divided by [S] and

Table 4. Absorption maxima for reaction mixtures and main reaction products of different reactions of the series – Mn^{II} catalysed periodate oxidation of anilines

Sl. no.	Aromatic amine oxidized	λ_{max} (nm)	Main reaction product
1.	Aniline	360	2,5-Dianilino- <i>p</i> -benzoquinoneimine
2.	<i>N</i> -Methylaniline	533	<i>p</i> -Benzoquinone
3.	<i>N</i> -Ethylaniline	534	<i>p</i> -Benzoquinone
4.	<i>p</i> -Ethylaniline	470	4-Ethyl-1,2-benzoquinone
5.	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylaniline	474	Tautomeric mixture of <i>O</i> -methyl-quinoneoxime and <i>p</i> -nitrosoanisole
6.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	470	Methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	475	4-Methoxy-1,2-benzoquinone
8.	<i>m</i> -Anisidine	472	4-Methoxy-1,2-benzoquinone
9.	<i>p</i> -Phenetidine	495	4-Ethoxy-1,2-benzoquinone
10.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	525	Methyl-1,4-benzoquinone
11.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	545	4-Methyl-1,4-benzoquinone
12.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	474	4-Methyl-1,2-benzoquinone
13.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	460	Chloro-1,4-benzoquinone
14.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	370	4-Chloro-1,2-benzoquinone
15.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	475	4-Chloro-1,2-benzoquinone
16.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	452	4-Bromo-1,2-benzoquinone
17.	4-Chloro, 2-methylaniline	490	5-Chloro, 3-methyl-1,2-benzoquinone
18.	5-Chloro, 2-methylaniline	484	2-Chloro, 5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone
19.	2,5-Xylidine	472	2,5-Dimethyl-1,4-benzoquinone
20.	2,3-Xylidine	469	2,3-Dimethyl-1,4-benzoquinone

Evaluation of pseudo first order rate constant :

As the k_{obs} (first order rate constant) values are essential to calculate the various thermodynamic parameters, the Guggenheim method³⁰ was applied to find out the k_{obs} values. Accordingly, a series of absorbance readings (equivalent to concentration of the intermediate being formed in the reactions), ' A_t ', is recorded at times t with equal intervals. A second series of readings $A_{t+\Delta t}$ is also made, each at time $t + \Delta t$, where Δt is arbitrary but constant interval of time chosen. A plot of $\log(A_{t+\Delta t} - A_t)$ vs t should give a straight line, with slope equal to $-k_1/2.303$. Hence k_{obs} , the first order rate constant, can be calculated from the slope. Before applying this method,

Mn^{II} to get the overall rate constant (k_{cat}). Here [S] is the concentration of the reactant taken in excess. As already mentioned, periodate was taken in excess.

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